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ixtisoslashgan ilmiy jurnal

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LITERATURE IS A REFLECTION OF THE SOUL AND CULTURE OF HUMANITY

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Abstract: This article presents various approaches to the periodization of the history of literature from ancient times to the present day. It explores the social context and inner life of humanity—realms accessible only through the art of language.

Key words: creation, humanity, language, literature, poetry, era, arts, writer, creativity.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada adabiyot tarixi davrlashtirilishining qadimgi davrlardan to hozirgi kungacha bo'lgan turli yondashuvlari taqdim etiladi. Unda insonning ijtimoiy hayoti va ichki kechinmalari – faqat so'z san'ati orqali ifodalab bo'ladigan jihatlar tahlil qilinadi.

Kalit so'zlar: ijod, insoniyat, til, adabiyot, she'riyat, davr, san'at, yozuvchi, ijodkorlik.

Аннотация: В данной статье представлены различные подходы к периодизации истории литературы от древности до наших дней. Рассматриваются социальная среда и внутренний мир человека – сферы, доступные только искусству слова.

Ключевые слова: творчество, человечество, язык, литература, поэзия, эпоха, искусство, писатель, креативность.

INTRODUCTION

Literature is one of the greatest creations of humankind, reflecting its culture, thoughts, emotions, and experiences. From ancient times to the present day, literature has served as a bridge between different eras and generations, allowing us to delve into the souls of people who lived before us and to understand the deeper aspects of human nature.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Various authors and dictionary compilers propose different versions of the periodization of literary history. The Brockhaus and Efron Encyclopedic Dictionary, published in the late 19th century, identified three periods in the history of Russian literature: from the earliest literary monuments to the Mongol-Tatar yoke; from the Mongol-Tatar yoke to the end of the 17th century; and from the 18th century to the time of the dictionary's publication (i.e., the end of the 19th century).

D.P. Svyatopolk-Mirsky, who published a two-volume history of Russian literature in London in 1927, distinguished the following periods: Old Russian (11th–17th centuries), the transitional period, the era of classicism, the golden age of poetry, the Gogol period, the era of realism, and the contemporary period starting from 1881 (following the death of F. M. Dostoevsky).

Published around the same time, The Literary Encyclopedia divided the periods of Russian literature into the following stages: Old Russian literature, 18th-century literature, 19th-century literature, 20th-century literature before the October Revolution, and 20th-century literature after the October Revolution. In general, literature is one of the ways to understand the world, humanity, and oneself. It best conveys the author's ideas, perspectives, and attitudes toward life and reality. Each writer creates an artistic world with which a particular reader may agree and connect. Just as a painter creates images of life on canvas, literature reflects people's lives and characters in a narrative form—similar to how they are portrayed in music and sculpture. The writer's primary tool is the word. Fiction is the art of language. Engaging with the world of art brings joy and selfless pleasure. This is why many people view the works of writers, composers, and artists as a source of leisure and enrichment.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Literature encompasses various forms of verbal art, including poetry, prose, drama, and essays. The term literature originates from the Latin word *litteratura*, meaning “the study of letters” or “knowledge of letters.” However, literature is more than a collection of written symbols—it is an expressive art form that conveys emotion, thought, and experience, evoking deep reactions and reflections in the reader. We often go to the cinema, watch TV, or use a computer to unwind or be entertained. Artists, composers, programmers, and writers, fully aware of the principles of their art, design their works to engage, inspire, and arouse curiosity in viewers and readers. Yet the significance of art in human life goes far beyond mere entertainment. No other art form can depict the human condition with the same depth and complexity as literature. While painting and sculpture can capture a moment in time, they cannot portray movement, transformation, or development. In contrast, cinema unites elements of literary art, theatre, painting, music, photography, and digital graphics. However, even cinema relies on literary scripts and cannot fully adapt lyrical works.

Despite cinema’s power, certain aspects of human inner life and social reality can only be conveyed through the written word. A writer can depict both a single fleeting moment and the span of an entire life, a solitary event or a complex chain of occurrences. Scientific and technological progress brings shifts in societal ideals and values, leading each new generation to seek new criteria for understanding and evaluating life.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

We are speaking of both the material and the spiritual, yet it is not easy to separate one from the other. Every powerful rise of literary thought that has influenced the upbringing of the younger generation always contains an element of spirituality. Higher technical and creative capabilities shape the thinking and lifestyle of young people. However, this by no means implies that youth should reject the highest spiritual and cultural values, nor should they become dependent on material wealth. There exists a concept known as the culture of the people, which is deeply rooted in national heritage and history. Throughout all eras, creators of verbal art have truthfully and comprehensively reflected the complexity and diversity of human life and society in their works. They vividly express their thoughts on the meaning of life and their innermost feelings. The author’s moral stance subtly influences the reader, who, while enjoying the text and becoming acquainted with remarkable characters, learns about the world and develops noble civic virtues.

In pedagogy, the concept of “formation” encompasses a variety of external (social, economic, educational, etc.) and internal (independent activity, self-education, etc.) factors that are inextricably linked and essential for the development of the individual. From this perspective, the successful formation of moral values depends on the combination of both external and internal conditions. It follows that, along with the educator’s efforts, students’ self-directed learning is essential for acquiring moral values, particularly for future philology specialists.

According to the principles of the learner-centered approach, students’ self-educational activities position them as active agents in the formation of their own moral values. This encourages the fullest expression of their autonomy and initiative in moral development. The literary works of A. S. Pushkin, M. Y. Lermontov, N. V. Gogol, L. N. Tolstoy, F. M. Dostoevsky, A. P. Chekhov, and M. Sholokhov enable the younger generation not only to learn about the past, but to live it alongside the characters, shaping their views, emotions, and character, nurturing a love for beauty, and fostering a willingness to strive for the triumph of good and truth.

Literature fosters a sense of beauty and enriches the human spirit. It most often portrays people from specific historical periods—their thoughts, emotions, interpersonal relationships, and ideals—thus revealing the inner and spiritual world of human beings. Like science, fiction possesses immense cognitive potential. It helps disseminate education and culture among the youth. Regardless of what themes authors address in their works, they always have the reader—humanity—in mind. This is why M. Gorky so accurately remarked that literature is the study of man.

CONCLUSION

The power of fiction lies primarily in its aesthetic influence. It is art that activates the spiritual powers of a person: the mind, intuition, emotions, and aesthetic perception. Aesthetic education nurtures in individuals the ability and need to perceive, understand, and appreciate beauty in all its forms and to embody it in life. It also fosters the capacity to comprehend the sublime, the tragic, and the comic. This complex and nuanced task of cultivating aesthetic sensibilities in the younger generation is fulfilled through the collaborative efforts of the family, school, and society.

Youth receive aesthetic education through the rich historical experience embodied in literary works. The aesthetic emotions stirred by a work of art facilitate the reception of social ideas not only through reason but also through emotional resonance, inspiring a proactive engagement with the life experiences depicted.

Literature ensures the intergenerational continuity of culture and its expanding universality. Through the creation of universally significant images that evolve into cultural symbols, it conveys the essence of historical progress. Figures such as Hamlet, Don Quixote, Prince Myshkin, and the Master and Margarita are no longer merely fictional characters—they represent universal human values. Reading works like Crime and Punishment, War and Peace, Anna Karenina, and The Garnet Bracelet transforms young people, reshaping their outlook on life and making them better individuals. These works touch their hearts and educate them deeply. Fiction is accessible to all, but the depth of its comprehension depends on the student's ability to read meaningfully, as well as on their own personality, preferences, and moral and ideological foundations.

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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
 - 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
 - 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
 - 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
 - 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
 - 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
 - 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
 - 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
 - 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
 - 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
 - 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
 - 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
 - 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

MAKTABGACHA VA MAKTAB TA'LIMI

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